

1 **Using Machine-Learning to Facilitate Data Extraction for Human Health Chemical**
2 **Assessments: A Proof-of-Concept Protocol**

3
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Data Availability and Deposition:

7 The data and/or code that support this work are will be made available in HAWC (build 0b3967cd)
8 and HERO (last updated April 3, 2024) at <https://hawc.epa.gov/assessment/100500328/> and
9 https://heronet.epa.gov/heronet/index.cfm/project/page/project_id/3591, respectively.
10 The Environmental Health Vocabulary is available at: <https://hawc.epa.gov/vocab/ehv/>
11 3rd Party Tools including the software applications Dextr (LaserAI beta version 1.1.0), SWIFT
12 Review (V1.43), and SWIFT Active Screener (V1.061.0794) are licensed applications.

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The statement "The authors declare they have no actual or potential competing financial interests" appears not to be true of all authors, given that some have a direct financial interest in LaserAI and are co-authors of the planned study. The authors may wish to adjust the declaration accordingly (as per journal policy, we don't ask authors to declare conflicts of interest, just to identify relevant interests and then manage them as necessary)

ABSTRACT

1 **Background:**

2 Systematic review (SR) methods are relied upon to develop transparent, unbiased, and
3 standardized human health chemical assessments. The expectation is that these assessments will
4 have discovered and evaluated all of the available information in a trackable, transparent, and
5 reproducible manner inherent to SR principles. The challenge is that chemical assessment
6 development relies on ~~consumption of~~ mostly literature-based data using manual approaches that
7 are not scalable. Various SR tools have increased the efficiency of assessment development by
8 implementing semi-automated approaches (human in the loop) for data discovery (literature
9 search and screening) and enhanced data repositories with standardized data collection and
10 curation frameworks. Yet filling these repositories with data extractions has remained a manual
11 process and connecting the various tools together in one interoperable workflow remains
12 challenging.

13 **Objectives:** The objective of this protocol is to ~~perform a proof of concept case study with a explore~~
14 incorporation of a new semi-automated data extraction tool (Dextr) ~~incorporated into a chemical~~
15 assessment workflow into a chemical assessment workflow and understand if the new tool
16 improves overall user experience. The semi-automated data extraction tool will be used to create a
17 literature inventory that will support the development of a Provisional Peer-Reviewed Toxicity
18 Value (PPRTV) assessment for 1,3-dinitrobenzene (DNB).

19 **Methods:** The workflow will use template Systematic Evidence Map (SEM) methods developed by
20 the Environmental Protection Agency for the identification of included studies. The methods
21 ~~sections of included studies will be the described~~ focus on ~~the~~ data extraction component of the
22 workflow into standardized template forms using ~~a fully both~~ manual ~~data extraction or and~~ semi-
23 automated (human in the loop) data extraction approach, based on machine learning (ML) models.
24 Both the manual and semi-automated data extractions will occur in Dextr. The new data extraction
25 tool will be evaluated for user experience and whether the manual and semi-automated workflows
26 will be evaluated and performances- data extracted using the automated approach meets or
27 exceeds metrics (precision, recall, and F1 score) for a fully manual data extraction will be
28 calculated.

1 **Discussion**

2 Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) methods have rapidly advanced and show
3 promise in achieving operational efficiencies in chemical assessment workflows by allowing
4 supporting ~~automated~~ or semi-~~automated~~ SR methods, possibly improving the user
5 experience. Yet incorporating advances into sustainable workflows has remained a challenge.
6 ~~Whether~~By using a tool like Dextr ~~that improves operational efficiencies and the user experience~~
7 ~~remains to be determined~~, ~~enables integration of AI/ML methods for users to readily use as part of~~
8 ~~their standard workflows~~, ~~chemical assessment teams can experience the operational efficiencies~~
9 ~~the advancements promise.~~

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1 The field of chemical assessment is an essential component of public health, aimed at
2 evaluating the hazards associated with environmental exposure for the purpose of protecting
3 human and environmental health. The Environmental Protection Agency's Chemical Pollutant
4 Assessment Division (CPAD) is tasked with developing various human health assessments that
5 evaluate all of the available information in a manner that is trackable, transparent, and unbiased.
6 CPAD has made significant advancements in assessment development processes by implementing
7 standardized workflows and tools that increase the efficiency of information review and
8 management (U.S. EPA, 2022) [\(Figure 1\)](#). A major challenge to assessment development has been
9 scaling traditional assessment approaches to meet the rate that information is made available and
10 organizing/sorting/labeling that information once it has been found. For example, PubMed covers
11 approximately 26,000 journals and contains approximately 36 million citations (accessed March
12 27, 2024).

13 Advantageously, as technological advances have improved access to information, they have
14 also advanced the methods, tools, and database management systems that assessment developers
15 use for finding and evaluating information. Use of tools, with auditing capability, that are web
16 accessible, support asynchronous collaboration, and use computationally intelligent approaches are
17 required to meet the demand for efficient and rapid development of systematic reviews [\(SR\)](#) and
18 systematic evidence maps (SEMs) (Thayer et al. , 2022; Thayer et al., 2023). While these tools
19 currently lack [full](#) automation [and require a human in the loop](#), up and coming [generative](#) artificial
20 intelligence (AI) move us toward it. The expectation is that [moving toward](#) automation using AI
21 models will help address the increasing demand to rapidly extract the information informing
22 assessments while adhering to foundational systematic (evidence mapping) methods. The
23 workflows ~~could become~~ [scalable and include with](#) the elasticity needed [to](#) rapidly scale (up or
24 down) and reuse previous work ~~and~~ in alignment with ~~with~~ FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible,
25 Interoperable, Reusable) (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

26 To date, the [machine learning \(ML\)](#)-assisted workflows implemented with SR tools and
27 similar applications have principally eased the human burden by decreasing the amount of time
28 spent screening studies at the title and abstract (TiAB) level, resulting in a significant reduction in

1 overall time and costs associated with screening ~~reviewed by (Van der Mierde et. al., 2019 (Howard~~
2 ~~et al., 2020). While these tools can facilitate the screening phase, they are not yet capable of~~
3 ~~automating the entire process, which includes complex tasks like data extraction and evidence~~
4 ~~synthesis. Therefore, Yet~~ summarizing the information available for decisions is still a challenge
5 because existing tools ~~and software applications for subsequent assessment~~ still heavily rely
6 ~~upon~~ manual user manipulation at each point in the workflow. Further, assessment teams in
7 general lack software developers and therefore the coding knowledge required to write
8 applications related to any form of large language model processing/AI. There are some tools with
9 user interfaces that require little to no coding knowledge, but interoperability gaps exist meaning
10 that coding knowledge is still required to migrate data between tool APIs. These gaps highlight
11 further the institutional barriers to acquiring the needed infrastructure for hosting all the
12 ~~information technology (IT)~~ components to fully enable intelligent document and data processing
13 workflows. Therefore, assessment teams must partner with coding experts ~~and~~ their institutions to
14 develop an ecosystem for developing the requirements ~~and~~ needed for an intelligent document
15 processing workflow, ~~as well as continue to feed in the while providing~~ training data needed ~~by~~
16 ~~coders to refine those ML models, for integration into existing tools and workflows.~~

17 Developing ~~machine learning ML~~ models for literature screening and data extraction ~~in~~
18 ~~biomedical and environmental research text~~ poses several additional challenges. First, research
19 involves a vast and diverse literature that spans multiple scientific disciplines, making it
20 challenging to identify and extract relevant information. Second, many studies use complex
21 methodologies, technical jargon, and highly specialized terminology, which can be difficult for
22 ~~machine learning ML~~ algorithms to comprehend. Additionally, the lack of standardized language and
23 terminology used in research can hinder the development of accurate ~~machine learning ML~~ models.
24 Third, the quality of the available data can be highly variable, and the data may be biased or
25 incomplete, which can lead to inaccurate results ~~and therefore models~~. Fourth, the interpretation of
26 results ~~in environmental chemical research~~ often requires a high level of domain expertise, making
27 it challenging to validate the performance of ~~machine learning ML~~ models by human experts.
28 Finally, ethical considerations, such as ensuring privacy and protecting sensitive information, must
29 be carefully considered when developing ~~machine learning ML~~ models for ~~any field, but in particular~~

1 environmental/biomedical text used to support decisions. Addressing these challenges will require
2 the integration of domain expertise, data quality control, and a collaborative effort between
3 computer scientists and environmental health researchers to develop robust and reliable machine
4 learningML models for literature screening and data extraction in environmental chemical
5 research.

6 In this paper, we describe a case application of AI/ML methods (i.e., incorporating them into
7 new or existing applications) in human health environmental chemical assessments. Data
8 extraction is currently one of the most laborious steps in the workflow and typically conducted by a
9 PhD level scientist. Therefore Our objective is exploratory as we seek to demonstrate
10 operationalization of an applicationunderstand the usability of a new data extraction tool (Dexter)
11 <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34920276/>, a web-based data extraction tool that provides a
12 user-verification workflow of ML predictions for data entities) in a chemical assessment workflow.
13 In thisThe exploratory case application, the goal is not to optimize model performance, but to
14 understand if the data extraction experience is improved with ML models (assisted by humans)
15 compared to a human only data extraction approach. assemble semi-automated data extraction into
16 a workflow using user friendly dashboards such that the information can be automatically
17 summarized into a SEM format.

18 2.0 METHODS

19 —This methodology focuses on the data extraction component of a chemical
20 assessment workflow (see Figure 1). This data extraction module will be used to will include
21 methodological steps for conducting an an evidence map SEM-based on the template methods for a
22 Provisional Peer-Reviewed Toxicity Value (PPRTV) as described in [(U.S. EPA, 2020), 10196824]}
23 and in accordance with the systematic review methods used to conduct the SEMs as outlined in the
24 Office of Research and Development (ORD) Staff Handbook for Developing Integrated Risk
25 Information (IRIS) Assessments (U.S. EPA, 2022). The specific steps methods developing the SEM,
26 including database are described below and will include literature searches and collecting
27 references, the Populations Exposure, Comparator, and Outcome (PECO) criteria, and literature
28 screening and tagging. literature screening, are described in the Supplemental Material, Appendices

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1 A-D literature inventory (including a new semi-automated data extraction tool), an optional study
 2 evaluation, and results visualization. The aim of this study was to understand the usability of a new
 3 semi-automated data extraction tool, Dexter, in a chemical assessment workflow, Dexter is a web-
 4 based, customized version of the Laser AI tool (<https://laser.ai>), a systematic review tool based on
 5 AI. Dexter includes features that allow creation of customized data extraction form templates with
 6 features such as ML models for data extraction of animal and human health studies, with the
 7 additional options to include data extraction fields based on flat or hierarchical vocabularies
 8 (picklists), and to relate data elements to each other. The underlying ML models underlying the
 9 data extraction in Dexter (were originally developed as part of NIST-TAC SRIE as described by
 10 (Nowake and Kunstman 2018 and Schmitt et al. 2018) with the additional Dexter features as
 11 described by (Walker et. al., 2022).

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12 **Figure 1.** The workflow for conducting a chemical assessment are described on the left. The tools listed
 13 on the right support modules in that workflow, particularly those colored in the green boxes. EPA's
 14 Health and Environmental Research Online (HERO) facilitates literatures searches and reference library
 15 management. Evidence Partner's DistillerSR, and Sciome's SWIFT-Active Screener and SWIFT-Review are
 16 useful literature screening and tagging tools. DistillerSR is also used for data extraction supporting SEM
 17

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1 development. EPA Health Assessment Workplace Collaborative (HAWC) is the primary content
2 management system for chemical assessments and facilitates reference, management, screening,
3 literature tagging, data extraction and visualization. Tableau is typically used to make available SEM
4 visuals. data and systematic review tools used within that workflow.

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5 ***2.1 Literature Search***

6 The literature search strategy will include a search of peer-reviewed and non-peer
7 reviewed data using the strategies described in the supplemental materials, (Appendix A and B).
8 The retrieved search results will be managed in HERO.

10 ***2.2 Literature Screening***

11 ***2.2.1 Prefilter***

12 Prior to screening, SWIFT Review (V1.43) will be used to filter search results. SWIFT
13 Review is a freely available interactive text mining work bench that allows users to search,
14 categorize, and visualize over-represented topics within titles and abstracts of a literature corpus
15 and priority rank published literature for manual screening (Howard et al., 2016). The results from
16 the literature search will be imported into SWIFT Review and filtered for the evidence streams
17 “animal (human health models)”, “human”, and “in vitro” prior to title and abstract screening.

18 ***2.2.2 Title and Abstract Screening***

19 Title and abstract screening and supplemental tagging will be done in SWIFT Active
20 Screener (V1.061.0794) in accordance with the Populations, Exposures, Comparators, and
21 Outcomes (PECO) statement and screening protocol as described in the Supplemental Materials
22 Appendices C and D. SWIFT Active screener is a web-based, collaborative systematic review
23 screening software and includes an active learning model that continuously predicts and updates
24 the list of unscreened studies based on the screened document list.

25 ***2.2.3 Full Text Screening and Tagging***

26 Full text screening will be done in Health Assessment Workspace Collaborative (HAWC) as
27 described in the Supplemental Materials, Appendix D. Health Assessment Workspace Collaborative
28 (HAWC) is a free, open-source web application that has features to support many steps involved in

1 the development and distribution of chemical assessments. Features include literature screening,
2 study evaluation or risk of bias evaluation, data extraction for animal bioassay and epidemiology
3 studies, and various data visualizations. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) manages a
4 deployment of HAWC (hawc.epa.gov) for EPA chemical assessments and that is used to carry out
5 work described here. All screening decisions will be tracked in HAWC as tags as described in the
6 supplemental materials appendix D.

7 **2.13 Semi-automated ~~D~~ata ~~E~~xtraction**

8 ~~Studies identified for inclusion based on full text screening will be extracted using Dextr~~
9 ~~(Walker et al., 2022). Dextr is a web-based software that supports semi-automated literature~~
10 ~~reviews in the field of environmental health. It is a customized version of the Laser AI tool~~
11 ~~(<https://laser.ai>). Dextr allows creation of data extraction form templates, including fields based on~~
12 ~~flat or hierarchical vocabularies (picklists). It also allows connecting machine learning models to~~
13 ~~specific fields to generate suggestions and text (PDF) highlights.~~

Commented [AM(3)]: Re there any papers on LaserAI that we can reference? Any papers on Dexter? Other than

14 **2.13.1 Data Extraction Strategy**

15 ~~Data extraction will occur from the methods section of the published study only and include~~
16 ~~the fields described in Tables 1 and 2 for animal toxicology and epidemiological studies,~~
17 ~~respectively. The repeated element to be extracted is indicated in the ML models and is attached to~~
18 ~~fields in the Dextr forms for automated extraction. The ML models in Dexter were previously~~
19 ~~trained exclusively from the methods sections of open access literature, therefore the data~~
20 ~~extraction here will similarly be restricted to the methods sections of literature meeting full text~~
21 ~~screening criteria (see Appendix C for PECO criteria and Appendix D for screening and tagging).~~
22 ~~The data extraction module of the workflow will be divided into two study arms: -manual data~~
23 ~~extraction (ME) and semi-automated data extraction (SE) as depicted in Figure 2, such that every~~
24 ~~reference will be extracted twice. The ME arm is designed to resemble the current review process~~
25 ~~with data extracted by one team member and QC by a different team member [as outlined in the~~
26 ~~Office of Research and Development (ORD) Staff Handbook for Developing Integrated Risk~~
27 ~~Information (IRIS) Assessments (U.S. EPA, 2022) and in (Thayer et. al., 2022)] using HAWC.~~
28 ~~In Therefore, in the ME arm, one of the data extractors reads each study and manually extracts text~~
29 ~~from the methods section into the data extraction fields (see Appendix E, Supplementary Tables 1~~

1 and 2). In the SE arm, one data extractor reviews the model-generated data extractions and
2 highlights. The data extractor makes corrections if needed to the extracted data to them, and
3 adding missing or removing extractions to fields as needed.

4 Both the ME and SE arms are implemented in Dexter using the fields described in Appendix
5 E. for animal toxicology studies (Supplemental Table 7) or human health studies (Supplemental
6 Table 8). The difference between the two arms and project set-up in Dexter is that there are no ML
7 models attached to the ME data extraction fields during project set-up. The MEs are also told to
8 manually highlight the relevant extracted text in the PDF during the extraction process to not only
9 facilitate QC, but also collect annotations that could be used for developing training data sets.

11 The results of extractions from ME and SE are then reviewed by two different quality
12 assurance (QA) reviewers. The QA reviewers will be blinded with-in regard to study arm allocation.
13 ~~The difference between the results of primary extraction and corrections applied by the QA~~
14 ~~reviewers will be used to calculate accuracy metrics for the primary extraction step. The time~~
15 ~~metrics will be calculated both for the primary extraction and QA steps to measure whether~~
16 ~~automatic text highlights provided alongside machine suggestions speed up the QA process. A~~
17 ~~primary extractor will review the model predictions to verify, edit, or delete the model predictions.~~
18 To control for differences between extractors' performance, the same extractors participate both in
19 ME and SE study arms. For each extractor, the references assigned to them will be randomized
20 across ME and SE in a 1:1 ratio. No extractor will extract or review the same reference across both
21 arms. Each study arm has a separate Dextr project with identical data extraction forms and fields
22 with picklists enabled. The ME project will not have any models attached to the fields in the data
23 extraction forms. To reduce variability associated with different levels of experience with the tool,
24 all reviewers will complete one hour training on how to use the tool and will be requiredasked to
25 perform extraction of two studies prior to starting the work. k. These two studies will not be
26 included in the metrics for -
27 ~~Dextr will track all user metrics data extraction or reviewer time including time to complete~~
28 ~~extraction.~~ Team members are instructed to not remain idle while signed into Dextr to ensure that
29 accurate recording of the time to complete extractions is logged. (Dexter automatically records the

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1 time users take to complete tasks). The times between start and stop actions will be manually
2 checked against the event log in Dexter to ensure there were no cases of an extraction task being
3 left idle, inflating the overall extraction time. Additionally, the user action logs from Dextr will be
4 filtered for any periods of inactivity longer than 5 minutes and excluded from the calculation of
5 time metrics. The data extractions will be exported from Dexter using the export feature. The
6 HAWC client is used to import the datasets into the HAWC project (HAWC, 2023). All data will be
7 available for download.

8 The difference between the results of primary extraction and corrections applied by the QA
9 reviewers will be used to calculate accuracy metrics for the primary extraction step. The time
10 metrics will be calculated both for the primary extraction and QA steps to measure whether
11 automatic text highlights provided alongside machine suggestions speed up the QA process. A
12 primary extractor will review the model predictions to verify, edit, or delete the model predictions.

13 Additionally, the user action logs from Dextr will be filtered for any periods of inactivity
14 longer than 5 minutes and excluded from the calculation of time metrics. The data extractions will
15 be exported from Dexter using the export feature. The HAWC client is used to import the datasets
16 into the HAWC project (HAWC, 2023). All data are also available for download.

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Figure 14. Data Extraction Teams. Two data extractors will independently extract data from references into forms using Dextr. The manual data extraction (ME) will manually extract all information while the semi-automated data extraction (SE) will manually extract all non-automated fields, while reviewing and correcting the model-generated extraction. Two different quality assurance (QA) reviewers will then correct both results for a given study to ensure accuracy of data extractions and calculate quality metrics.

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2.24 Evaluations of Workflow and Model Performance semi-automated data extraction in the SEM workflow

The aim of this evaluation will be to understand how using the tool the integration of Dextr will perform as a semi-automated data extraction tool in an assessment workflow. The primary goals were to understand if the overall Dexter user experience was favorable and if the SE arm performed equal to or better than the ME arm. The evaluation will focus on the first pass data extraction, prior to QA results will not be incorporated into the first pass model performance metrics due to the potential to introduce complexity in resolving disagreements between reviewers.

First pass model performance will be evaluated manually and based on human review of the primary, and to also understand specifically how the semi-automated extraction

1 recall, precision, and extraction time compared to manual extraction. The evaluation plan described
2 below is similar to the approaches previously described by (Walker et al., 2022).

3 **2.4.1 Dexter Model Performance**

4 ~~Results from Dexter will be~~ A collection of metrics that include recall, precision, and F-1
5 ~~score from selected data extraction fields from animal (test article name, species, strain, sex and~~
6 ~~endpoint) or human (study population source, chemical name, exposure measurement type) will be~~
7 ~~evaluated initially. Results will be calculated by comparing the extracted data after primary~~
8 ~~extraction within each data extraction arm. Precision is the number of correct positive predictions~~
9 ~~made and is represented by the true positives/(true positives + false positives). Recall quantifies~~
10 ~~the number of correct positives made out of all correct positives that could have been made and is~~
11 ~~represented by true positives/(true positives + false negatives). The precision and recall score will~~
12 ~~be combined into a single F measure (the harmonic mean or F1 score) for summarizing overall~~
13 ~~model performance within a field. The F-measure will be calculated as~~
14 ~~(2*precision*recall)/(precision + recall), calculated by automatically comparing the extracted data~~
15 ~~after primary extraction and QA.~~

16 A collection of metrics will be generated including, but not limited to, precision, recall, and
17 F1 score. Precision is defined as the fraction of ~~The extracted data elements will be evaluated within~~
18 ~~an experimental arm for the number of correct data points entered for a specific field (i.e. test~~
19 ~~article name) from the primary extraction among all the primary extraction data points within a~~
20 ~~field. A data point will be marked as a “true positive” if it matches with the same element in the~~
21 ~~primary extraction +QA (i.e. when the human does not change the model response). A data point~~
22 ~~will be marked as a “false positive” if the element is included in the primary extraction by the~~
23 ~~model, but not included in the primary extraction +QA (i.e. a human makes a change to the model~~
24 ~~response). A data point will be marked as a “false negative” if the element is missed by the model in~~
25 ~~the SE arm and included by human in the manual extraction. A data point will be marked as a true~~
26 ~~negative when the model and the human do not fill in a field. True negatives will be identified by~~
27 ~~comparing data extracts to gold standard data available within HAWC (ORD SEM PFAS 150 (2022) |~~
28 ~~HAWC (epa.gov) and <https://hawc.epa.gov/assessment/100500328/>).~~

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1 ~~The time metrics will be calculated both for the primary extraction and QA steps from both~~
2 ~~arms to measure the total extraction time for comparing the manual vs semi-automated arms. Total~~
3 ~~time for both the primary extraction as well as the time for QA will be evaluated. Recall is defined as~~
4 ~~the fraction of correct data points from primary extraction among all instances of a fields being~~
5 ~~correctly populated by either the primary extraction or the QA step. F1 score is defined as the~~
6 ~~harmonic mean of precision and recall.~~

7 ~~Although not the primary goal of the current protocol, the manually curated results can be~~
8 ~~incorporated back into the models to refine the model's performance and then redeployed in Dextr.~~
9 ~~In subsequent projects, the new model performance can be reevaluated. Over time, it is expected~~
10 ~~that model performance will improve given that more data are available for training. The~~
11 ~~sustainable workflow is explicitly intended to include a human such that the workflow is semi-~~
12 ~~automated and model performance can be evaluated and improved with routine use of ML-~~
13 ~~facilitated data extraction over time.~~

14 ***2.3 Usability Feedback***

15 ~~After completing the data extraction, user experience will be qualitatively through~~
16 ~~questionnaire (Appendix F, Supplemental Table 9).~~

18 ***2.5 User metrics for data extraction across platforms***

19 ~~User metrics include the number of fields for each form, study type, and time spent~~
20 ~~reviewing a data extraction form. User metrics will be collected from Dextr. Analyses will be~~
21 ~~performed with the user metrics compared to past projects. Each extractor and reviewer will report~~
22 ~~on user experience while using Dextr both for user experience and user interactions. In addition,~~
23 ~~general observations on the extraction process will be solicited from extractors. This input can~~
24 ~~inform future development of Dextr or similar software.~~

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2.46 Data Storage

All data generated by the workflow describe here will be stored in HAWC and HERO at <https://hawc.epa.gov/assessment/100500328/> and https://heronet.epa.gov/heronet/index.cfm/project/page/project_id/3591, respectively.

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2.57 Caveats and Limitations

This study will include extraction of 20 papers ~~previously extracted as~~ the primary intent is to evaluate the workflow (versus evaluation of model performance). ~~In the event~~ Due to the novelty of the application, plausible estimates of the effect values across time and accuracy metrics are unknown, therefore formal sample size calculations are not provided, but are based on prior user and developer experience with Dexter.

The study is designed to inform US EPA application of semi-automated extraction tools. Hence, the workflow and data extraction forms resemble the ones used at US EPA. These conditions may not apply elsewhere, so the study results may not generalize to all settings in which literature reviews of environmental agents are performed.

Although not the primary goal of the current protocol, the manually curated results can be incorporated back into the models to refine the model's performance and then redeployed in Dexter. In subsequent projects, the new model performance can be reevaluated. Over time, it is expected that model performance will improve given that more data are available for training. The sustainable workflow is explicitly intended to include a human such that the workflow is semi-automated and model performance can be evaluated and improved with routine use of ML-facilitated data extraction over time.

Table 1. Animal Data Extraction Fields

Domain/Field Name	Picklist or free text	Help text	Model ?
Test article	Domain heading	Domain heading	
Test article name	Free-text	Select the chemical name (test material) as reported by authors and the appropriate link to chemical information (if available) from the CompTox Chemicals Dashboard.	Yes
CAS number	Free-text	Select the appropriate CAS number.	Yes

Vehicle	Free text	Description of the vehicle (use name as described in methods but also add the common name if the vehicle was described in a non-standard way).	Yes
Route of exposure	Picklist Oral Inhalation Dermal Subcutaneous Intraperitoneal Intravenous Other Not reported	Description of the primary route of exposure. If multiple primary exposures, select 'Other', highlight appropriate text, and provide details in the comments section.	Yes
Study	Domain heading		
Experiment type	Picklist Short-term (1-30 days) Subchronic (30-90 days) Chronic (>90 days) Mechanistic Reproductive Developmental Other Acute (<24 hr)	Select experiment type as appropriate	
Animal model	Domain heading	Domain heading	
Species	Picklist	Select species as appropriate from the picklist. If not available from the picklist select 'Other', highlight appropriate text, and provide details in the comments section.	Yes
Strain	Picklist	Select strain as appropriate. If not available from the picklist select 'Other', highlight appropriate text, and provide details in the comments section.	Yes
Sex	Picklist Male Female Combined Not reported	Select sex as appropriate.	Yes
Endpoint	Domain heading	Domain heading	

Endpoint name	Picklist Available endpoint names can be found at https://hawc.epa.gov/vocab/ehv/ (Endpoint/Outcome column)	From the picklist select the relevant endpoint addressed by this study summary.	Yes
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Table 2. Epidemiology Data Extraction Fields

Field	Choices	description	Semi-automated?
Study characteristics	Domain heading	Domain heading	
Study design	Picklist cohort case-control RCT Ecological Cross-sectional Other Not reported	Select the most appropriate design from the list. If more than one study design applies (e.g., a cohort with cross-sectional analyses of baseline measures), can either a) select one design ("cohort") and clarify different timing in remaining extraction or b) select "other" and provide details in comments.	Yes
Population	Domain heading	Domain heading	
Study population source	Picklist Occupational General population Other	Describe the source of the study population.	No
Overall study population (N)	Free text	Describe numerically the number of participants in the study population	No
Population age category	Picklist Adults Children and adolescents 1-18 yrs Pregnant women Infants <1 yr Other Not reported	Select the most appropriate population age category from the list.	No
Population age details	Free Text	Describe the study population's age category.	No

sex	Picklist Male Female Male and Female Not reported	Description of population sex	No
Country	Free Text	Describe the country of residence of the study population	No
Additional geographic information (optional)	Free text	Optional field, describe additional geographic information regarding the study population.	No
Exposure	Domain heading	Domain heading	
Chemical name	Free text	This field is commonly used in visualizations, so consider using a common acronym, e.g., BPA instead of Bisphenol A	Yes
Exposure measurement type	Picklist Biomonitoring Blood (portion: Plasma) Blood (portion: Whole blood) Blood (portion: Serum) Urine Teeth Nails Hair Saliva Breast milk Semen Feces Cerebrospinal fluid Exhaled breath Other Air Food Drinking water Occupational Modeled Questionnaire Direct administration – oral Direct administration – inhalation	Select the most appropriate type from the list. If a study includes multiple exposure measurement types but they are analyzed with outcomes separately, create a separate entry for each. If more than one type is combined for analysis with an outcome, you can select multiple options from the list. "Occupational" should be used when the exposure is based on job duties, etc. (i.e., not occupational exposure measured by biomarkers or air).	No
Exposure route	Picklist Inhalation Oral Dermal	Description of the primary route of exposure. If multiple primary exposures, select 'Other', highlight appropriate text,	Yes

	In-utero Intravenous Unknown/Total Other Not reported	and provide details in the comments section.	
Outcomes	Domain heading	Domain heading	
Outcome name	Picklist See Supplemental Materials, Appendix E	A unique name for the specific outcome being measured. The endpoint is generally more specific than the effect (e.g., total cholesterol, incident asthma within the previous year, WISC-IV full scale). Use controlled vocabulary when available. If not available, enter outcome as free text.	Yes

1

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